

TAX ADMINISTRATION REFORM IN UZBEKISTAN

Tashkent State University of Economics
Faculty of "Taxes and Budget Accounting"
Deputy Dean, Docent, **Ergashov I.O**

ilhomjonergashev777@gmail.com

Tashkent State University of Economics
Faculty of "Taxes and Budget Accounting",
student **Ummatova B.X**

bonuummatova05@gmail.com

Abstract: Further improvement of the tax system, which is considered an integral component of the country's economy, the functioning of the administration in a systematic way, is one of the pressing issues. This article emphasizes the importance of developing measures to improve the relationship between tax authorities and taxpayers, eliminate existing problems, and gives personal conclusions to this issue, which are obtained as a result of studying theoretical sources.

Keywords: Tax system, administration, efficiency of reforms, fiscal policy, volatility of fiscal revenues, analysis of mixed methods, stability of state revenues, state budget, state economic stability

Introduction: Today, in the context of the modernization of the country's economy, the role of the state in regulating the economy is increasing, and tax policy, including tax administration, is primarily an important tool in implementing the goals and objectives set. As is known, the main goal of reforming the tax system is to further develop production and stabilize the economy by reducing the tax burden on taxpayers. We believe that this goal can be achieved only through the implementation of a consistent tax policy. In recent years, special attention has been

paid to tax reforms in our republic, and the trend towards a fundamental reform of the activities of tax authorities, simplification of tax legislation, and support for business entities is being consistently implemented. In this regard, it is of particular importance that the Decrees and resolutions recently adopted by our President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev are aimed at simplifying tax policy, developing entrepreneurship, stimulating the social sector, reducing the tax burden, and improving tax administration. Improving the tax administration of our country is primarily aimed at increasing the efficiency and quality of tax relations between taxpayers and the state, which is one of the main directions of our tax policy. For this reason, our President considers increasing the level of tax administration as an important direction of tax policy, as a potential reserve for reducing the tax burden, ensuring equality of competition among honest taxpayers, and reducing the costs associated with the operation of the tax system. It is no coincidence that the Action Strategy, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 dated February 7, 2017 - "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", identifies the most important tasks for 2017-2021 as the systematic simplification of the taxation system, the reduction of the tax burden by expanding the tax base, and the introduction of modern methods of tax administration¹.

In the decree of PF-5116 adopted on July 18, 2017 on the implementation of these tasks, our president noted the following problems in the implementation of the tax administration, the current tax system of which is in particular its important direction²:

- the complexity of the taxation system and the insufficiently unified nature

¹ Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017-PF-4947 on the strategy of action for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan

² Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev No. 5116 dated 30.03.2018 "On measures to radically improve tax administration and increase the collection of taxes and other mandatory payments"

of taxes with the same tax base, the volatility of tax legislation, the inability of taxpayers to fully fulfill their tax obligations;

- to increase the legal culture of taxpayers aimed at ensuring their constitutional duty to pay taxes voluntarily, especially if the work carried out on the premises has not been improved at the level of demand;

- the fact that the absence of mechanisms of external control over the activities of the tax authorities to ensure the completeness of revenues to the state budget does not make it possible to expand the tax base, increase the complexity of taxes and take into account taxpayers;

- the fact that the organizational structure of the tax authorities does not allow to fully cover the objects of taxation and expand the tax base, as well as timely collection of taxes and other mandatory payments, replenishment of state and local budget revenues, mobilize existing resources;

- the state of implementation of modern information and communication technologies in the activities of tax authorities does not fully ensure the transparency of tax administration, cooperation with interested ministries and departments in taxation issues and the effectiveness of the use of public services.

The imperfection of the mechanisms for organizing tax control, reducing the effectiveness of detecting tax violations and their premature prevention, is observed in an increase in the appeal of taxpayers to judicial authorities. Analysis of the situation and development trends of tax-related legal relations requires improving the activities of reliable forecasting of tax revenues, developing promising directions of tax policy, forming its regulatory legal base, organizational and methodological aspects for the sustainable development of tax administration using advanced foreign experience.

In recent years, the tax administration of our country has been radically reformed. In December 2019, the new edict tax code was adopted, introducing direct applicable norms. As a result of this, it is noted that entrepreneurs have

increased confidence in reforms, and tax revenues have increased 4 times in the data. The fact that the value-added tax has reached 152,000 from 6,000 payers lies in the fact that the tax rate is reduced from 15% to 12%, of course.

The head of our state specifically emphasizes the need to improve the activities of tax authorities, the widespread introduction of Information Technology for this. As a result of this, the processes are fully automated, tax barriers are eliminated to reduce the size of the “hidden economy”, the personnel potential is strengthened. Of particular importance is the need to ensure the stability of tax revenues in the rapidly changing, complex situation in the world, to provide support to entrepreneurs. "I came here to represent taxpayers," the president said. It is not at all the main thing that revenue increases to us now. First of all, we need to make the system correct, teach those who do not know, reduce the tax burden and establish the free, honest operation of entrepreneurs. Taxers should be helpers, not punishers”³.

As mentioned, in some cases, many questions also arise because entrepreneurs do not understand the new program and requirements. Therefore, on the principle of” taxpayer – assistant", it is necessary to teach them to work in a new way, to increase the coverage of electronic services.

“It's wrong to walk around just because we're doing right. Why should we be offended by them now that people are dissatisfied? Your biggest problem is that you haven't explained. That's wrong. Leaders at all levels in the tax authority should often meet with entrepreneurs, people, hear their problems, prevent misunderstandings, give, teach and be close supporters of the necessary information in social networks, Media,” the head of state said during his visit to the state tax committee.

³ From the speech of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev on March 16, 2022 in the continuation of his visit to the state tax committee

During the visit, it was also mentioned that the tax system should actively participate in the transformation of state-owned enterprises, provide them with guidance on lowering the cost and financial stability.

It is known that in accordance with the decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan of November 4, 2020, a Fiscal Institute was established under the state tax committee. The head of state also paid special attention to the quality of training. It was noted that it is important to train employees of tax authorities on new IT programs being introduced in the system, as well as to improve the qualifications of specialists abroad.

Personally, I am in favor of the fact that it is necessary to effectively organize the activities of tax authorities and form a system free of corruption in the process of working with taxpayers. A system with transparency, transparency, justice develops, in which the participants in the relationship also fulfill their obligations with a sense of satisfaction, and if we say that at the bottom of this, the movement in solidarity for the development of the country is reflected, then we will not be mistaken.

Conclusion:

It is important to systematically improve the administration of the tax system and improve the relationship between the tax authorities and taxpayers. This process serves to eliminate issues, develop activities and further develop the country's economy. Based on the conclusions drawn from theoretical sources, the most important part of the independent and effective development of tax law and the tax system will be known.

During this process, the relationship between the tax authorities and taxpayers should be more intense, in order to divide the processes of making tax payments, we often have to respond to problems in tax time and other measures. It is also very important to use technical means to update the tax system, automate and increase transparency.

For the further development and independent functioning of the country's economy, efforts to improve the tax system and strengthen the relationship between the tax authorities and taxpayers are very important. This process helps ensure transparency, efficient management and administration of the tax system.

To improve the tax administration and strengthen the relationship between tax authorities and taxpayers, I recommend the following private proposals:

1) Open information should be provided about the activities carried out by the tax authorities and the work of the tax system. This creates clarity about the tax system and its work for individuals and organizations.

2) with the help of automation of the tax system and the use of technical means, it will be easier for taxpayers to use the system and will help ensure effective management of tax law.

3) to strengthen the relationship between tax authorities and taxpayers, it is very important to create a well-structured and reliable communication system. Through open channels and single points of contact, it will be possible to quickly and efficiently solve problems and proposals.

4) it is very important to provide continuing education to employees in tax authorities and taxpayers, to develop the industry and adapt to innovations. This will help further develop the tax system and increase administration.

5) providing open consultation services to help taxpayers, help solve problems quickly and efficiently, and strengthen relationships.

The above proposals will help to make the tax system more effective, increase administration and strengthen the relationship between tax authorities and taxpayers. This process provides additional support for the development of the country's economy.

References:

Regulatory and legal documents

1. Tax Code
2. Presidential Decrees and Decrees

Internet resources

1. <http://www.info.gov.hk>
2. <http://www.uzreport.com>
3. <http://www.finance.uz>
4. <http://www.mf.uz>
5. <http://www.banxso.ore.mx>
6. <http://www.nbp.pl>
7. <http://www.mas.gov.sg>
8. <http://www.resbank.so.ra>
9. <http://www.snb.uz>
10. <http://www.bol.or.th>
11. <http://www.soliq.uz>
12. <http://www.my.soliq.uz>